

Comment 1

Comment 2

Acquisition Parameter

Date of acquisition 2021-06-18T14:02:17.218+02:00
Acquisition method name D:\Methods\flexControlMethods\Specification\LP_12kDa.par
Acquisition operation mode Linear
Voltage polarity POS
Number of shots 100
Name of spectrum used for calibration
Calibration reference list used

Instrument Info

G:\His- en D-His-1 Maldi-Tof\His-1\1Lin

<i>User</i>	BDAL@US
<i>Instrument</i>	MICRO-FLEX-PC
<i>Instrument type</i>	microflex